

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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THE IMPACT OF GAMES ON STUDENTS' LEARNING, MOTIVATION AND ENGAGEMENT

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Annotation: The role of the gamified learning environment in current life and its effects on students' learning, motivation and participation are explored in this article. As well as it discusses the advantages and disadvantages of using games to teach students. Just like a coin has two sides, the game-based teaching approach has not only a good, but also a bad influence on students' academic knowledge, attendance and behavior. While advancing problem-solving skills, critical thinking and knowledge retention, the modern method might result in many downsides, such as distraction and over-reliance on gamification.

Keywords: gamification, game-based teaching approach, gamified learning, motivation, engagement, participation, problem-solving skills, digital games, implementation, right concept, reward, critical thinking, passion, challenge, productivity, traditional teaching method, opportunity.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'yinlashtirilgan o'quv muhitining hozirgi hayotdagi o'rni va uning talabalarning o'rganishi, motivatsiyasi va ishtirokiga ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Shu bilan birga, talabalarni o'qitish uchun o'yinlardan foydalanishning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari muhokama qilinadi. Tanganing ikki tomoni bo'lganidek, o'yinga asoslangan o'qitish uslubi talabalarning akademik bilimi, faolligi va xulq-atvoriga nafaqat yaxshi, balki yomon ta'sir ham ko'rsatadi. Muammoni hal qilish, tanqidiy fikrlash va bilimlarni esda tutish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish bilan birga, zamonaviy usul ko'plab salbiy natijalar ko'rsatishi mumkin, masalan, chalg'itish va o'yinga haddan tashqari bog'lanib qolish.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается роль геймифицированной среды обучения в современной жизни и ее влияние на обучение, мотивацию и участие студентов. Кроме того, в ней обсуждаются преимущества и недостатки использования игр для обучения студентов. Так же, как у монеты есть две разные стороны, игровой подход к обучению имеет не только хорошее, но и плохое влияние на академические знания, посещаемость и поведение студентов. Несмотря на развитие навыков решения проблем, критического мышления и сохранения знаний, современный метод может иметь много недостатков, таких как отвлечение внимания и чрезмерная зависимость от геймификации.

Ключевые слова: геймификация, игровой подход к обучению, игровое обучение, мотивация, вовлеченность, участие, навыки решения проблем, цифровые игры, реализация, правильная концепция, вознаграждение, критическое мышление, страсть, вызов, продуктивность, традиционный метод обучения, возможность.

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Introduction. Nowadays, the utilization of educational games has become prevalent in the realm of education. The reason is that there is growing evidence to suggest that gamification is increasingly being accepted as an effective learning strategy. There is a word “Gamification”, that might be unknown to some people. What is the “Gamification”? Gamification seems like a bit difficult concept, but it makes the lesson easier, it is useful for both of educator and the student. Gamification - the practice of making activities more like games in order to make them more interesting and enjoyable. In usual, it is used for straightening the students' performance, and knowledge and teaching them effectively in education. Based on empirical evidence from recent studies, the success of digital games in education has sought to validate the effects of gamification in support of its potential to improve motivation, engagement, and social influence while allowing students to immerse in experiential learning (Groening & Binnewise, 2019; Lopes & Tucker, 2019). In addition, implementing a gamified teaching approach significantly increases student participation and enhances learning outcomes. However, it is important to choose a game that is appropriate for the lesson. The teachers who use game-based task must focus on the right concepts and clear goals, considering how to make the lesson more interactive (Fitria et al., 2022). Otherwise, using games that are irrelevant to the topic will cause a number of drawbacks, such as wasting time and getting less knowledge.

I think that games, whether digital or non-digital, have been widely acknowledged as potent tools that amplify student motivation and engagement. Traditional pedagogical methods often struggle to maintain students' attention, resulting in disengagement and reduced learning outcomes. However, game-based learning introduces interactive and immersive experiences that make it enjoyable and effective. High-quality, affordable, adaptable and joyful educational services could be delivered through educational games, effectively enhancing the connection between learning materials, educators and students (Gentry et al., 2019).

The advantages of the game on students' motivation, performance and learning

In modern life, the development of gamification is progressively flourishing within the realm of education (Arifudin et al., 2021). In view of the fact that there are many benefits of the game-based educational method, including enhanced engagement and motivation, encouraging collaboration and social skills, improved problem-solving skills, critical thinking and knowledge retention.

Enhancement of enthusiasm. Games are powerful tools for maintaining student engagement and preventing boredom. By incorporating games, teachers can

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encourage healthy competition among students. When learning is gamified, individuals will participate more actively and with greater enthusiasm due to factors such as rewards, challenges and competition. While participating in educational games, students will encounter many obstacles, and they try to overcome them to achieve rewards and to be the first and the best among group mates.

Encouragement of social skills. It is important to work together to achieve a common goal in many games. So participants communicate to give instructions or discuss with teammates and opponents. As a result of this, verbal and non-verbal social-emotional skills are improved. As well as teamwork can help us to reduce shyness and keep away from isolation.

Enhancing decision-making and critical thinking. Game-based learning can improve students' logical thinking and problem-solving abilities by challenging participants to analyze situation, make a quick decision, predict outcomes and evaluate disparate options. Sandbox games are the best examples of games that boost such lateral thinking skills. In this game student have to control an avatar and investigate a virtual world and take a quick decision independently (Hwang et al., 2015). While players are playing these games, they make mistakes in making the right decisions, but after realizing the mistakes, they try to avoid repeating them in the future. Firstly, the teachers have to instruct how to play for promoting productiveness and insight (Adipat et al., 2021).

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Drawbacks of gamification. Gamified teaching method is dependent on rewards, such as points, badges or leader-boards. Rewards can not only increase the curiosity, but also shift the focus from actual learning. Students think much more about prizes instead of paying attention to educational elements that they can learn. The next challenge that arises under the influence of a gamified approach is not equally suitable for all topics. For many subjects, traditional teaching methods are more effective compared to gamification.

Conclusion. Gamification presents both challenges and opportunities. By thoughtfully implementing gamified learning, we can encourage students to participate more actively in the learning process, as game-based teaching significantly enhances interactivity, enjoyment and immersion. Students are attracted to game elements, such as rewards, challenges, and competition. As well as we can conclude that this approach has a good influence on improving logical thinking and collaboration. Despite the fact that it has several disadvantages, gamification is commonly used in education due to its efficiency.

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